

Title : **Solid-state rechargeable battery with tunneling effect.**

Adolfo Pastore

Federico II University of Naples

Faculty of Physics

Naples

Italy

(Independent researcher)

Abstract.

The system functions as a rechargeable battery using the tunneling effect. It consists of two superimposed conductive foils, one aluminum and the other graphite, subjected to a special electrochemical protocol. The two foils are placed one on top of the other in a "sandwich" shape. The system therefore comprises an aluminum foil and a graphite foil. The aluminum foil is roughened through a mechanical abrasion process and then subjected to an electrochemical process that generates a surface effect known as "pitting corrosion." The same electrochemical process also allows for the electrodeposition of graphene oxide. After undergoing the electrochemical process, the aluminum foil exhibits surface roughness and roughness in the order of micrometers and nanometers, with a statistical distribution that can reach several thousand pits on the surface. The surface roughness can be seen as many micro-tips that, when subjected to the action of the electric field, produce a phase-dependent tunneling effect, transferring electrons to the graphite foil. The two foils are overlapped with light pressure and connected to a DC power supply. Depending on the distance between the foils, this generates an intense electric field between the overlapping layers. The electrons coming from the roughness of the aluminum plate connected to the negative pole tunnel through the thin layer of graphene oxide and accumulate on the graphite surface connected to the positive pole of the DC power supply. The voltage measured between the plates disconnected from the power supply is in the order of 2.4 V. The current generated is in the order of a few tens of mA, enough to light a low-power LED for over 12 hours. The cell does not use membranes and is not immersed in any electrolytic solution.

Introduction.

The operation of the rechargeable cell mimics that of the scanning tunneling microscope (STM), according to a well-known quantum mechanical phenomenon. Indeed, if a potential difference is applied between a very thin metal tip held close to a conductive surface at a distance of a few angstroms, electrons can tunnel through the void between the tip and the surface. Reflecting on this phenomenon, the possibility of using a metal surface roughened by mechanical abrasion and subjected to surface pitting corrosion through an electrochemical process was envisioned. The basic idea was to imagine that the countless irregular roughnesses could be interpreted as edges of micrometer dimensions, which could be considered sharp points. Therefore, it was believed that the surface roughness of the aluminum, under the action of the electric field, could behave like many sharp points, producing a multiple tunneling effect in phase. First, the aluminum foil must be subjected to a specific electrochemical protocol.

Electrochemical protocol.

FIG.1

FIG.2

FIG. 1 shows a container containing a NaCl electrolyte solution with a conductivity of 15,000 microS/cm. Fig. 1 shows the electrolyte solution in which two graphite and aluminum foils are immersed. The aluminum foil has undergone a mechanical abrasion process before undergoing the process we are illustrating. A DC voltage is applied between the foils, connecting the aluminum to the positive terminal and the graphite to the negative terminal. The applied voltage must initially be around 5 V and is slowly increased gradually until reaching a value of 12 V, which corresponds to a current of approximately 3 A depending on the geometric characteristics of the foils used. The foils are energized for approximately 2 hours. This process promotes the formation of pitting corrosion. After this phase, the foils are removed and stacked in a sandwich shape, held together by an insulating clamp. The pair of overlapping plates is immersed in the same electrolytic solution, but connecting the aluminum electrode to the negative pole and the graphite electrode to the positive pole, see FIG. 2. A voltage of 5 V is applied, gradually increasing until reaching 12 V. The pair of plates is left in the electrolytic solution for at least 30 minutes. The pair of plates is removed and placed on a horizontal surface, continuing to supply it with the same voltage of 12 V. The current will tend to decrease from a value of a few amperes until it reaches 700 mA. The voltage is slowly increased until a value of 25 V is reached, keeping this value constant. The current will tend to decrease over time. Wait the time necessary for the current to reach zero. After this process, the pair of graphite-aluminum electrodes is suitable for use as a rechargeable cell.

During the electrochemical phase, the following occurs:

a localized corrosion process (consumer pitting), as Cl⁻ ions penetrate the passive Al₂O₃ film. Even if aluminum is placed at the cathode, anodic microzones form and the aluminum oxidizes, Al = Al⁺³ + 3e.

The Al⁺³ ions react with OH⁻ generated at the cathode to form Al(OH)₃. Then, at the anode (graphite), the chlorine ions are oxidized,

forming highly reactive chlorine gas.

At the aluminum cathode, water reduction occurs:

If Al⁺³ is present due to corrosion, it can react with OH⁻ to form:

The main redox reactions are:

Gas Cl₂ at the anode,

H₂ at the cathode

Al(OH)₃

Al⁺³ due to corrosion

OH⁻ and H⁺, which locally alter the pH.

The formation of localized pitting on the aluminum surface superimposed on the graphite surface gives the aluminum foil a pitting density of several hundred pits/cm². These asperities have a random shape, but also include point-shaped irregularities of micrometer and nanometer dimensions that can cause tunneling. See **FIG. 3**.

FIG. 3 SEM image of pits corrosion for Al.

Materials and Methods.

The following equipment, materials, and instruments were used to conduct the experimental verification:

(N.B.: The dimensions of the graphite and aluminum foils may be smaller.)

- 1) 500 W DC power supply with cooling fan.
- 2) Parallelepiped graphite plate with a rectangular base, 15 mm thick, 45 mm wide, and 100 mm long.
- 3) Thin aluminum foil, 20 mm thick, 60 mm wide, and 100 mm long.
- 4) Voltmeter with a 30 V range.
- 5) Voltmeter with a 10 V range.
- 6) Ammeter with a 20 A range.
- 7) Ammeter with a 100 mA range.
- 8) High-resolution optical microscope.

Physical characteristics of the cell.

Experimentally, it has been found that the charging voltage for the cell can vary from 8 V to 30 V with charging currents in the order of a few tens of mA. Charging times can be in the order of tens of minutes, depending on the charging voltage. The cell voltage as a function of time, measured after charging, has an initial peak of 3.3 V, which after a brief transient stabilizes at 2.4 V, according to a trend that remains to be explored with regard to the analytical formula. It is assumed that it has an exponential time dependence, and the same can be assumed for the second descending segment. See **FIG. 4**.

FIG.4 Voltage-time graph for cell discharge

Physical interpretation of the tunneling effect on the cell.

The local electric field between the plates can be expressed as: $E \propto V / r$, where r is the radius of curvature of the tip.

The electrons tunnel through the thin dielectric layer of graphene oxide and accumulate on the opposite graphite surface.

Therefore, the charge is localized and stable; the transferred charges are concentrated in microregions.

When the power is removed, these charges do not redistribute completely. The system stabilizes at a fixed residual voltage, related to the geometric configuration of the asperities. The behavior is nonlinear. The system does not follow the linear law valid for conventional capacitors: $Q = C V$ where Q is the stored charge, C is the capacitance, and V is the voltage, as the effective capacitance is not uniform.

The charge transfer occurs by field emission tunneling, not by classical conduction. The nanometer asperities act as microtunnel emitters,

generating a stable residual voltage even after the power supply is removed.

We can estimate the tunnel current density and the local field at a tip. Let's consider three important aspects:

- 1) Local electric field at the tips.
- 2) Tunnel current density (Fowler–Nordheim equation).
- 3) Estimation of the transferred charge and residual voltage.

Assuming that the tunnel current lasts for a time t (for example, 1 s), and that the active surface is $A = 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$ (nano-area):

$$Q = J A t$$

If $J \approx 10^{-3} \text{ A/m}^2$, then:

$$Q \approx 10^{-3} \times 10^{-8} \times 1 = 10^{-11} \text{ C}$$

Assume that the capacitance between the surfaces is $C \approx 4 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F}$ (typical value for closely spaced plates in relation to those used):

$$V(\text{residual}) = Q / C = 10^{-11} / 4 \times 10^{-12} \approx 2.5 \text{ V}$$

This value is closest to the experimentally measured value.

The model based on tunneling from nanometer asperities reasonably interprets the residual voltage of 2.4 V after removing the power supply. This behavior was derived using:

- a) electric field amplification.
- b) tunneling (Fowler–Nordheim).
- c) geometric capacitance.

Obviously, the cumulative effect of all the tips distributed across the graphite surface according to a specific statistical distribution must be considered.

Indeed, since the surface is rough, thousands of microtips contribute, each with the potential to generate tunneling.

Assuming that the surface has a spike density n (number of spikes per m^2), each spike contributes a tunnel current density J_p . If we denote the active surface area with A , we have:

$I(\text{total}) = n A J_p$, therefore the total transferred charge Q is:

$$Q(\text{total}) = I(\text{total}) t = n A J_p t$$

$$V(\text{residual}) = Q(\text{total}) / C$$

Assuming that all the spikes emit in phase with each other and the field is uniform.

1) Electric field on the asperities (tips)

The asperities act as microtips with a very small radius of curvature r . The local electric field E is amplified compared to the mean field:

$$E = \beta \cdot V / d$$

where:

V = applied voltage

d = distance between the surfaces (~fractions of a mm)

β = field amplification factor, which depends on the tip geometry and can be on the order of 10^4 – 10^6

For nanometer tips, β can be very high, so E can reach values on the order of 10^9 V/m.

2) Tunneling current: Fowler–Nordheim equation.

The tunnel current density J for field emission is given by:

$$J = (A E^2 / \phi) \exp(-B \phi^{3/2} / E)$$

where:

$$A \approx 1.54 \times 10^{-6} \text{ A eV V}^{-2}$$

$$B \approx 6.83 \times 10^9 \text{ V eV}^{-3/2} \text{ m}^{-1}$$

ϕ = work function of the material (in eV, for Al \approx 4.2 eV)

E = local electric field

Suppose we have the following data for the cell:

$$V = 30 \text{ V}$$

$$d = 0.1 \text{ mm} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$$

$$\beta = 10^5 \text{ therefore } E = 30 \text{ V} \times 10^5 / 10^{-4} = 3 \times 10^9 \text{ V/m}$$

$$\phi = 4.2 \text{ eV.}$$

$$J \approx (1.54 \times 10^{-6} \times (3 \times 10^9)^2 / 4.2) \cdot \exp(-6.83 \times 10^9 \times 4.2^{3/2} / 3 \times 10^9)$$

$J \approx$ a few mA/cm², a significant current on the nanometer scale.

FIG. 5

Charged cell powering a 1/4 W white LED.